

Neutrosophic Crisp Set & relations

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Abstract. In a world full of indeterminacy, traditional crisp set with its boundaries of truth and false has not infused itself with the ability of reflecting the reality. Therefore, neutrosophic found its place into contemporary research as an alternative representation of the real world. In this paper, we aim to develop a new type of neutrosophic crisp sets called the *-Neutrosophic crisp sets as a generaliza-

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1 Introduction

Established by Florentin Smarandache in 1980, Neutrosophy was presented as the study of the origin, nature, and scope of neutralities, as well as their interactions with different ideational spectra. The main idea was to consider an entity, "A" in relation to its opposite "Non-A", and to that which is neither "A" nor "Non-A", denoted by "Neut-A". And from then on, Neutrosophy became the basis of neutrosophic logic, neutrosophic probability, neutrosophic set, and neutrosophic statistics.

In [31, 32, 33], Smarandache introduced the fundamental concepts of neutrosophic set, that had led Salama et al. in [5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30], to provide a mathematical treatment for the neutrosophic phenomena which already existed in our real world.

Moreover, the work of Salama et al. formed a starting point to construct new branches of neutrosophic mathematics. Hence, Neutrosophic set theory turned out to be a generalization of both the classical and fuzzy counterparts [1, 2, 12, 22, 34].

This paper is devoted for introducing a new type of neutrosophic crisp set coded the *- neutrosophic crisp set, and studying some of its properties. And hence, we present and study the notion of *- neutrosophic relation and some of its properties.

tion of the star intuitionistic set introduced by Indira et al.[4], and hence studying some of its properties. To this end we will investigate the notion of *-Neutrosophic relation and some of its properties.

2 Terminologies

We recollect some relevant basic preliminaries, and in particular, the work of Smarandache in [31, 32, 33], and Salama et al. in [5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30]. Smarandache introduced the neutrosophic components T, I, F which represent the membership, indeterminacy, and non-membership values respectively, where $]0, 1[$ is nonstandard unit interval.

3 *- Neutrosophic Crisp Sets

We shall now consider some possible definitions for a new type of neutrosophic crisp set

Definition 3.1

Let X be a non-empty fixed set. A neutrosophic crisp set (NCS for short) A is an object having the form $A = \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle$.

Then we define the *- neutrosophic set A^* as $A^* = \langle A_1 \cap (A_2 \cup A_3)^c, A_2 \cap (A_1 \cup A_3)^c, A_3 \cap (A_1 \cup A_2)^c \rangle$ where A_1, A_2 and A_3 are subsets of X such that

$$M = A_1 \cap (A_2 \cup A_3)^c, \quad S = A_2 \cap (A_1 \cup A_3)^c \text{ and} \\ R = A_3 \cap (A_1 \cup A_2)^c.$$

A *- neutrosophic crisp set is an object having the form $A^* = \langle M, S, R \rangle$

Lemma 3.1

Let X be a non-empty fixed sample space. A neutrosophic crisp set (NCS for short) A is an object having the form $A = \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle$. Then

$A^* = \langle A_1 \cap (A_2 \cup A_3)^c, A_2 \cap (A_1 \cup A_3)^c, A_3 \cap (A_1 \cup A_2)^c \rangle$ is also a neutrosophic crisp set.

Proof

It's clear.

Corollary 3.1

Let X be a non-empty fixed set. Then ϕ_N^* and X_N^* are also neutrosophic crisp set.

Theorem 3.1

Let X be a non-empty fixed sample space, two neutrosophic crisp sets A, B are having the form

$A = \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle, B = \langle B_1, B_2, B_3 \rangle$, and two *- neutrosophic sets $A^* = \langle M_1, S_1, R_1 \rangle, B^* = \langle M_2, S_2, R_2 \rangle$ where

$$M_1 = A_1 \cap (A_2 \cup A_3)^c, S_1 = A_2 \cap (A_1 \cup A_3)^c, \\ R_1 = A_3 \cap (A_1 \cup A_2)^c, M_2 = B_1 \cap (B_2 \cup B_3)^c, \\ S_2 = B_2 \cap (B_1 \cup B_3)^c, \text{ and}$$

$$R_2 = B_3 \cap (B_1 \cup B_2)^c, \text{ Then } A \subseteq B \text{ implies } A^* \subseteq B^*.$$

Proof

Given $A \subseteq B$. Then it is easy to prove that $M_1 \subseteq M_2, S_1 \subseteq S_2, R_1 \supseteq R_2$ or $M_1 \subseteq M_2, S_1 \subseteq S_2, R_1 \supseteq R_2$ So $A^* \subseteq B^*$.

Remark 3.1

- 1) All types of ϕ_N^* and ϕ_N are concedes.
- 2) All types of X_N^* and X_N are concedes.
- 3) $A^* = B^*$ iff $A^* \subseteq B^*$ and $B^* \subseteq A^*$.

Definition 3.8

Let X be a non-empty set, and $A^* = \langle M, S, R \rangle$ be a *- neutrosophic crisp set on a NCS $A = \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle$ where $M = A_1 \cap (A_2 \cup A_3)^c, S = A_2 \cap (A_1 \cup A_3)^c, R = A_3 \cap (A_1 \cup A_2)^c$, Then the complement of the set A^* (A^{*c} , for short) may be defined as three kinds of complements

$$(C_1) \text{ Type1: } A^{*c} = \langle M^c, S^c, R^c \rangle,$$

$$(C_2) \text{ Type2: } A^{*c} = \langle R, S, M \rangle,$$

$$(C_3) \text{ Type3: } A^{*c} = \langle R, S^c, M \rangle.$$

Definition 2.3

Let X be a non-empty fixed set, two neutrosophic crisp sets A, B are having the form $A = \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle, B = \langle B_1, B_2, B_3 \rangle$, and two *- neutrosophic crisp

sets $A^* = \langle M_1, S_1, R_1 \rangle, B^* = \langle M_2, S_2, R_2 \rangle$ where

$$M_1 = A_1 \cap (A_2 \cup A_3)^c, S_1 = A_2 \cap (A_1 \cup A_3)^c, \\ R_1 = A_3 \cap (A_1 \cup A_2)^c, M_2 = B_1 \cap (B_2 \cup B_3)^c, \\ S_2 = B_2 \cap (B_1 \cup B_3)^c, \text{ and} \\ R_2 = B_3 \cap (B_1 \cup B_2)^c, \text{ Then}$$

1) $A^* \cap B^*$ may be defined as two types:

$$\text{i) Type1: } A^* \cap B^* = \langle M_1 \cap M_1, S_2 \cap S_2, R_3 \cup R_3 \rangle \text{ or}$$

$$\text{i. Type2: } A^* \cap B^* = \langle M_1 \cap M_1, S_2 \cup S_2, R_3 \cup R_3 \rangle$$

4) $A^* \cup B^*$ may be defined as two types:

$$\text{i) Type1: } A^* \cup B^* = \langle M_1 \cup M_1, S_2 \cap S_2, R_3 \cap R_3 \rangle \text{ or}$$

$$\text{ii) Type2: } A^* \cup B^* = \langle M_1 \cup M_1, S_2 \cup S_2, R_3 \cap R_3 \rangle.$$

Lemma 3.1

Let A^*, B^* are *- neutrosophic crisp sets. Then $A^* - B^* = A^* \cap B^{*c}$
It easy to show that L. H. S is also a *- neutrosophic crisp sets.

Example 3.2

Let $X = \{a, b, c, d, e, f\}$, $A = \langle \{a, b, c, d\}, \{e\}, \{f\} \rangle$,
 $B = \langle \{a, b, c\}, \{d\}, \{e\} \rangle$, $C = \langle \{a, b\}, \{c, d\}, \{e, f, a\} \rangle$
 $D = \langle \{a, b\}, \{e, c\}, \{f, d\} \rangle$ are NCS. Then
 $A^* = \langle \{a, b, c, d\}, \{e\}, \{f\} \rangle$, $B^* = \langle \{a, b, c\}, \{d\}, \{e\} \rangle$,
 $C^* = \langle \{b\}, \{c, d\}, \{e, f\} \rangle$,

The complement may be equal as:

1)

$$A^{*c} = \langle \{e, f\}, \{a, b, c, d, f\}, \{a, b, c, d\} \rangle,$$

$$A^{*c} = \langle \{\{f\}, \{e\}, \{a, b, c, d\}\}, A^{*c} = \langle \{\{f\}, \{a, b, c, d\}, \{a, b, c, d\}\} \rangle,$$

$$2) C^{*c} = \langle \{a, c, d, f\}, \{a, b, e, f\}, \{a, b, c, d\} \rangle,$$

$$C^{*c} = \langle \{e, f\}, \{c, d\}, \{b\} \rangle, C^{*c} = \langle \{e, f\}, \{a, b, e, f\}, \{b\} \rangle.$$

3) $A^* \cup B^*$ may be equals the following forms

$$A^* \cup B^* = \langle \{a, b, c, d\}, \{e\}, \phi \rangle,$$

$$A^* \cup B^* = \langle \{a, b, c, d\}, \phi, \{f\} \rangle,$$

4) $A^* \cap B^*$ may be equals the following forms

$$A^* \cap B^* = \langle \{a, b, c\}, \{e, d\}, \{f, e\} \rangle,$$

$$A^* \cap B^* = \langle \{a, b, c\}, \phi, \{f, e\} \rangle,$$

Proposition 3.1

Let $\{A_j^* : j \in J\}$ be arbitrary family of *- neutrosophic crisp subsets on X , then

1) $\bigcap A_j^*$ may be defined two types as :

- i) Type1: $\cap A^*_j = \langle \cap M_j, \cap S_j, \cup R_j \rangle$, or
- ii) Type2: $\cap A^*_j = \langle \cap M_j, \cup S_j, \cup R_j \rangle$.
- 2) $\cup A^*_j$ may be defined two types as :
 - i) Type1: $\cup A^*_j = \langle \cup M_j, \cap S_j, \cap R_j \rangle$ or
 - ii) Type2: $\cup A^*_j = \langle \cup M_j, \cup S_j, \cap R_j \rangle$.

Corollary 3.2

Let $\{A_i\}$ be a NCSs in X where $i \in J$, where J is an index set and $\{A_i^*\}$ are corresponding *- neutrosophic crisp subsets on X then

- a) $A_i^* \subseteq B^*$ for each $i \in J \Rightarrow \cup A_i^* \subseteq B^*$.
- b) $B^* \subseteq A_i^*$ for each $i \in J \Rightarrow B^* \subseteq \cup A_i^*$.
- c) $(\cup A_i^*)^c = \cap A_i^{*c}; (\cap A_i^*)^c = \cup A_i^{*c}$.
- d) $A_i^* \subseteq B^* \Leftrightarrow B^{*c} \subseteq A^{*c}$.
- e) $A^{*c} = A$,
- f) $\phi_N^{*c} = X_N; X_N^{*c} = \phi_N^*$.

Now we shall define the image and preimage of *- neutrosophic crisp set.

Let X, Y be two non-empty fixed sets and $f: X \rightarrow Y$, be a function and $A = \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle$, $B = \langle B_1, B_2, B_3 \rangle$ are neutrosophic crisp sets on X and Y respectively, $A^* = \langle M_1, S_1, R_1 \rangle$, $B^* = \langle M_2, S_2, R_2 \rangle$ be the *- neutrosophic crisp sets on X and Y respectively.

Definition 3.9

- (a) If B^* is a *- NCS in Y , then the preimage of B^* under f , denoted by $f^{-1}(B^*)$, is a *- NCS in X defined by $f^{-1}(B^*) = \langle f^{-1}(M_2), f^{-1}(S_2), f^{-1}(R_2) \rangle$
- (b) If A^* is a *- NCS in X , then the image of A^* under f , denoted by $f(A^*)$, is the *- NCS in Y defined by $f(A^*) = \langle f(M_1), f(S_1), f(R_1)^c \rangle$.

Here we introduce the properties of images and preimages some of which we shall frequently use in the following.

Corollary 3.2

Let $A^*, \{A_i^* : i \in J\}$, be a family of *- NCS in X , and $B^*, \{B_j^* : j \in K\}$ *- NCS in Y , and $f: X \rightarrow Y$ a function.

Then

- (a) $A^*_1 \subseteq A^*_2 \Leftrightarrow f(A^*_1) \subseteq f(A^*_2)$,
 $B^*_1 \subseteq B^*_2 \Leftrightarrow f^{-1}(B^*_1) \subseteq f^{-1}(B^*_2)$,
- (b) $A^* \subseteq f^{-1}(f(A^*))$ and if f is injective, then $A^* = f^{-1}(f(A^*))$,
- (c) $f^{-1}(f(B^*)) \subseteq B^*$ and if f is surjective, then $f^{-1}(f(B^*)) = B^*$,
- (d) $f^{-1}(\cup B^*_i) = \cup f^{-1}(B^*_i)$, $f^{-1}(\cap B^*_i) = \cap f^{-1}(B^*_i)$,

- (e) $f(\cup A^*_i) = \cup f(A^*_i)$; $f(\cap A^*_i) \subseteq \cap f(A^*_i)$; and if f is injective, then $f(\cap A^*_i) = \cap f(A^*_i)$;
- (f) $f^{-1}(Y^*_N) = X^*_N$, $f^{-1}(\phi^*_N) = \phi^*_N$.
- (g) $f(\phi^*_N) = \phi^*_N$, $f(X^*_N) = Y^*_N$, if f is surjective.
- (h) If f is surjective, then $(f(A^*))^c \subseteq f(A^*)^c$. if furthermore f is injective, then have $(f(A^*))^c = f(A^*)^c$.
- (i) $(f^{-1}(B^*))^c = (f^{-1}(B^*))^c$.

Proof

Clear by definitions.

4 *- Neutrosophic Crisp Set Relations

Here we give the definition relation on *- neutrosophic crisp sets and study of its properties.

Let X, Y and Z be three ordinary nonempty sets

Definition 4.1

Let X be a non-empty fixed set, two neutrosophic crisp sets A, B are having the form $A = \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle$,

$B = \langle B_1, B_2, B_3 \rangle$, and two *- neutrosophic crisp

sets $A^* = \langle M_1, S_1, R_1 \rangle, B^* = \langle M_2, S_2, R_2 \rangle$ where

$$M_1 = A_1 \cap (A_2 \cup A_3), S_1 = A_2 \cap (A_1 \cup A_3),$$

$$R_1 = A_3 \cap (A_1 \cup A_2),$$

$$M_2 = B_1 \cap (B_2 \cup B_3), S_2 = B_2 \cap (B_1 \cup B_3), \text{ and}$$

$$R_2 = B_3 \cap (B_1 \cup B_2), \text{ Then}$$

- i) The product of two *- neutrosophic crisp sets A^* and B^* is a *- neutrosophic crisp set $A^* \times B^*$ given by

$$A^* \times B^* = \langle M_1 \times M_2, S_1 \times S_2, R_1 \times R_2 \rangle \text{ on } X \times Y.$$

- ii) We will call a *- neutrosophic crisp relation $R^* \subseteq A^* \times B^*$ on the direct product $X \times Y$.

The collection of all *- neutrosophic crisp relations on $X \times Y$ is denoted as $SNCR(X \times Y)$

Definition 4.2

Let R^* be a *- neutrosophic crisp relation on $X \times Y$, then the inverse of R^* is denoted by R^{*-1} where $R^* \subseteq A^* \times B^*$ on $X \times Y$ then $R^{*-1} \subseteq B^* \times A^*$ on $Y \times X$.

Example 4.1

Let $X = \{a, b, c, d, e, f\}$, $A = \{\{a, b, c, d\}, \{e\}, \{f\}\}$,

$B = \{\{a, b, c\}, \{d\}, \{e\}\}$, are NCS.

Then $A^* = \{\{a, b, c, d\}, \{e\}, \{f\}\}$, $B^* = \{\{a, b, c\}, \{d\}, \{e\}\}$, then

the product of two *- neutrosophic crisp sets given by

$$A^* \times B^* = \{((a, a), (a, b), (a, c), (b, a), (b, b), (b, c), (c, a), (c, b), (c, c)), ((e, d)), ((f, e))\}$$

and

$$B^* \times A^* = \{((a, a), (a, b), (a, c), (a, d), (b, a), (b, b), (b, c), (b, d), (c, a), (c, b), (c, c), (c, d)), ((d, e)), ((e, f))\}$$

, and $R^*_1 = \{\{(a, a)\}, \{(c, c)\}, \{(d, d)\}\}$, $R^*_1 \subseteq A^* \times B^*$ on

$X \times X$,

$$R_2^* = \langle \{(a,b), \{(c,c), \{(d,d), (b,d)\}\} \rangle R_2^* \subseteq B^* \times A^* \text{ on } X \times X, R_1^{*-1} = \langle \{(a,a), \{(c,c), \{(d,d)\}\} \rangle \subseteq B^* \times A^* \text{ and } R_2^{*-1} = \langle \{(b,a), \{(c,c), \{(d,d), (d,b)\}\} \rangle \subseteq B^* \times A^* .$$

We can define the operations of *- neutrosophic crisp relations.

Definition 4.3

Let R^* and S^* be two *- neutrosophic crisp relations between X and Y for every $(x, y) \in X \times Y$ and NCSS A and B in the form $A = \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle, A^*$ on X , $B = \langle B_1, B_2, B_3 \rangle, B^*$ on Y Then we can defined the following operations

i) $R \subseteq S$ may be defined as two types

a) Type1: $R^* \subseteq S^* \Leftrightarrow M_{1R} \subseteq M_{1S}, S_{1R} \subseteq S_{1S},$

$$R_{1R} \supseteq R_{1S}$$

b) Type2:

$$R^* \subseteq S^* \Leftrightarrow M_{1R} \subseteq M_{1S}, S_{1R} \supseteq S_{1S}, R_{1R} \supseteq R_{1S}$$

ii) $R^* \cup S^*$ may be defined as two types

a) Type1:

$$R^* \cup S^* = \langle M_{1R} \cup M_{1S}, S_{1R} \cup S_{1S}, R_{1R} \cap R_{1S} \rangle,$$

b) Type2:

$$R^* \cup S^* = \langle M_{1R} \cup M_{1S}, S_{1R} \cap S_{1S}, R_{1R} \cap R_{1S} \rangle.$$

iii) $R^* \cap S^*$ may be defined as two types

a) Type1:

$$R^* \cap S^* = \langle M_{1R} \cap M_{1S}, S_{1R} \cup S_{1S}, R_{1R} \cup R_{1S} \rangle,$$

b) Type2:

$$R^* \cap S^* = \langle M_{1R} \cap M_{1S}, S_{1R} \cap S_{1S}, R_{1R} \cup R_{1S} \rangle.$$

Theorem 4.1

Let R^*, S^* and Q^* be three *- neutrosophic crisp relations between X and Y for every $(x, y) \in X \times Y$, then

$$i) R^* \subseteq S^* \Rightarrow R^{*-1} \subseteq S^{*-1}.$$

$$ii) (R^* \cup S^*)^{-1} \Rightarrow R^{*-1} \cup S^{*-1}.$$

$$iii) (R^* \cap S^*)^{-1} \Rightarrow R^{*-1} \cap S^{*-1}.$$

$$iv) (R^{*-1})^{-1} = R^*.$$

$$v) R^* \cap (S^* \cup Q^*) = (R^* \cap S^*) \cup (R^* \cap Q^*).$$

$$vi) R^* \cup (S^* \cap Q^*) = (R^* \cup S^*) \cap (R^* \cup Q^*).$$

vii) If $S^* \subseteq R^*, Q^* \subseteq R^*$, then $S^* \cup Q^* \subseteq R^*$.

Proof

Clear

Definition 5.4

The *- neutrosophic crisp relation $I^* \in SNCR^*(X \times X)$, the *- neutrosophic crisp relation of identity may be defined as two types

i) Type1: $I^* = \langle \{A^* \times A^*\}, \{A^* \times A^*\}, \phi^* \rangle$

ii) Type2: $I^* = \langle \{A^* \times A^*\}, \phi^*, \phi^* \rangle$

Now we define two composite relations of *- neutrosophic crisp sets.

Definition 5.5

Let R^* be a *- neutrosophic crisp relation in $X \times Y$, and S^* be a neutrosophic crisp relation in $Y \times Z$. Then the composition of R^* and S^* , $R^* \circ S^*$ be a *- neutrosophic crisp relation in $X \times Z$ as a definition may be defined as two types

i) Type1:

$$R^* \circ S^* \leftrightarrow (R^* \circ S^*)(x, z)$$

$$= \cup \{ \langle (M_1 \times M_2)_R \cap (M_1 \times M_2)_S \rangle,$$

$$\{ (S_1 \times S_2)_R \cap (S_1 \times S_2)_S \}, \{ (R_1 \times R_2)_R \cap (R_1 \times R_2)_S \} \} .$$

ii) Type2:

$$R^* \circ S^* \leftrightarrow (R^* \circ S^*)(x, z)$$

$$= \cap \{ \langle (M_1 \times M_2)_R \cup (M_1 \times M_2)_S \rangle,$$

$$\{ (S_1 \times S_2)_R \cup (S_1 \times S_2)_S \}, \{ (R_1 \times R_2)_R \cup (R_1 \times R_2)_S \} \} .$$

Theorem 4.2

Let R^* be a *- neutrosophic crisp relation in $X \times Y$, and S be a *- neutrosophic crisp relation in $Y \times Z$ then $(R^* \circ S^*)^{-1} = S^{*-1} \circ R^{*-1}$.

Proof

Let $R^* \subseteq A^* \times B^*$ on $X \times Y$ then $R^{*-1} \subseteq B \times A$,

$S^* \subseteq B^* \times D^*$ on $Y \times Z$ then $S^{*-1} \subseteq D^* \times B^*$, from Definition 4.3 and similarly we

can $I^*_{(R^* \circ S^*)^{-1}}(x, z) = I^*_{S^{*-1}}(x, z)$ and $I^*_{R^{*-1}}(x, z)$ then

$$(R^* \circ S^*)^{-1} = S^{*-1} \circ R^{*-1} .$$

Conclusion and Future Work

In this paper, a new generalization of the star intuitionistic set called the *-Neutrosophic crisp sets was introduced. The properties and some basic operations relevant to the new type was investigated. Furthermore, the notion of *-Neutrosophic relation and some of its properties were studied. For the future, we intend to introduce the new concepts presented in this paper to some possible applications in computer and mathematics.

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